

Situation of Today's Indian News Media and Influence Reflection Through Political Comic Strips

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Description

Last 15 years India has changed a lot especially, as media electoral and print both grows beyond human reach (Bhattacharya 2019; Chatterjee 2007; Goswami 2016; Lacity and Rudramuniyaiah 2009). The fourth pillar going through a big crisis. Impartial reporting has gone, no more fact. However, as recent events, the media are facing big challenges. Freedom of speech is no more freedom. Now everything is linked with nationalism and religion. Every day the politicians are spreading hate speeches through the media. Nowadays the media plays a dreadful role, whether it is through spreading spades in the name of religion. Nowadays investigative journalism has lost its charm, the reporting style is very poor, and the content also zeroes the research base. Through the following graphic novel (Figure 1) the author tried to point out how “Godi Media” affects common people's life (Chakraborty and Chowdhury 2022).

Figure 1. Graphic novels used to show the status of the current role of Indian media.

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Now-a-days, the media is not talking about common man's problems (e.g. high cost of living or mehangai), rather the media is trying to engage people with unnecessary information and infotainment. Indian citizens (at grassroot level) are not conscious about high cost of living and proactively not protesting against it, instead they are sleeping. Although, Indian media could have helped people to be conscious about high cost of living and protest against it.

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